

NATIONAL VALUES ARE A MIRROR OF SPIRITUALITY

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Annotation. This article discusses national values and their preservation, traditions and programs.

Keywords: nationality, programs, traditions, values.

National values are a philosophical concept that expresses the unique characteristics, features, signs, and symbols of each nation, and represent its contribution and share in the national cultural heritage formed in the process of social development that that nation has undergone. This same national identity, its own identity, finds expression in the culture of the nation, literature, art, language, religion, historical memory, way of life, work, and thinking, customs, paintings, and festivals. National values are an expression of national-spiritual culture and are the product of each nation's worthy contribution to the treasury of humanity.

Today, it is important to protect ourselves from various ideological attacks, to preserve our national values, traditions, and practices that have been honed over the centuries, and to live by them. National values are the rich cultural heritage, customs, traditions and moral standards of our ancestors, through which qualities such as patriotism, morality, respect and humanity are instilled in the future generation.

National values are important in forming high qualities in the minds of young people. And correctly conveying them to the younger generation is one of the main tasks of teachers, parents and the general public. In this regard, the role of family upbringing, educational institutions and cultural and educational events is invaluable. National values can be instilled in the younger generation through cultural and educational events. Conferences, exhibitions, competitions and concerts on the topic of national values enrich the worldview of young people in this regard, form in them a sense of respect for national values.

National values include not only knowledge and skills for the younger generation, but also the goal of appreciating the heritage of our ancestors and passing it on to future generations. By respecting national values, it is also possible to form a sense of national pride and honor in the younger generation. This, in turn, helps to educate them as independent thinkers who should deeply understand their culture and history.

National values serve as a solid foundation in the personal development of young people and help them not to be separated from their national identity in the process of globalization. Self-awareness, understanding and appreciation of their identity are achieved as a result of the upbringing of the younger generation on the basis of national values. In this process, not only educational institutions, but also the general public, that is, each member of society, must contribute their share.

By widely promoting our national values, increasing content on our national culture in the media, the Internet and social networks, it is possible to strengthen the sense of respect for national values in the younger generation. At the same time, the use of modern technologies in the process of introducing young people to our national values is also of great importance.

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We also need to strengthen respect for national values not only in the process of upbringing and education, but also by practicing them in our daily lives. The younger generation must learn to practice its national values every day, to accept them as an integral part of their lives.

For this, it is important to widely promote and adhere to national values in families, educational institutions and public places. Raising the future generation in the spirit of national values is important not only for their personal development, but also for the stability and future of our entire society. Our youth, respecting national values, will ensure the continuity of our national culture by preserving them and passing them on to future generations. Therefore, let each of us accept respect for national values as an integral part of our daily lives and educate the younger generation in this spirit. Through this, we will be able to raise a highly cultured, independent and conscious generation in the future, who will respect their national values. Respect for national values not only strengthens the bond between generations, but also plays an important role in ensuring the moral and spiritual development of young people. Through national values, young people deeply understand their identity, history, cultural heritage and the value of their ancestors.

This process also contributes to the upbringing of young people as responsible, humane and loyal individuals to their Motherland. Respect for national values ensures that the younger generation lives in a society based on the principles of mutual respect, dialogue and solidarity. A person who respects their national values also respects the values of representatives of other nations and cultures. This forms qualities such as openness to different cultures, tolerance and solidarity. Today, as globalization further expands cooperation and dialogue between different nations and cultures, these qualities are of particular importance.

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